

Learning Practices among Higher Education Students in Hooghly District: Challenges and Prospects

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Abstract: Learning is consistent; we all learned from various situations at any stage. Students have different learning styles or study habits in respect to their environmental or genetic factors. Many studies shows that the academic success of students depends on their good study habits. This study investigated the status of higher education students' study habits in the Hooghly District and identified the numerous challenges they are facing in their academic life. Quantitative and Qualitative both methods of research were used in this study. Data were collected from 239 UG students from different colleges in the Hooghly District of West Bengal. A study habits inventory was employed to measure students' study behaviour through various dimensions. The study highlighted that there is a significant difference between the joint family and nuclear family in terms of their study habits, which means the family structure of students may affects students study habits. Various challenges are also being explored based on secondary sources such as lack of family awareness, limited infrastructure, etc.

Keyword: study habit, higher education, environmental, genetic, academic success.

Introduction:

Learning is a process through which a student acquires knowledge or skills from the environment. Through learning, a student gains and understands new information (Collins Concise Dictionary & Thesaurus of English Language, 2002). A good study environment, good educators and study habits, etc. are the main contributors to the achievement of better learning outcomes by the students in schools (Robinson, 2000). Study habits refer to the disciplined methods through which students' study; they manage their time well (Oxford Dictionary & Thesaurus of English Language, 2003). Danskin and Burnett (1952); S. V. Kiester & Kiester (1992) said that study habits are more significant in academic success of students and students with good study habits score higher than other students. Academic performance is a key indicator used to evaluate students' learning achievement. At the end of the semester, the cumulative learning gains represent students' learning outcomes, and the effective time students dedicate to their studies plays a significant role in their academic performance. Consistency in study routines and effective time management can significantly affect a student's ability to retain knowledge for a long time.

Study habit is a important key factor that influence academic performance. These include various strategies that enhance the learning process and make students more focused. Various studies have reported many different study habits that have a positive effect on students' academic achievement. Global research has indicated the effects of study habits on the academic achievement of students (Abid et al. 2023; Reza & Alireza 2014; İlçin et al. 2018; Proctor et al. 2006).

This study seeks to analyse the study behaviour of higher education students in the Hooghly district. The researcher tries to examine how their study habits in-

fluence academic achievement, and explores the major challenges faced by undergraduate and postgraduate students in that district. Hooghly district, a district of West Bengal state, which is part of India. Chinsurah is the headquarters of the district. The four subdivisions are Chinsurah Sadar, Chandannagore, Serampore and Arambagh.

Review of Literature:

Mahwish et al. (2017) examine the relationship between academic performance of students and their study habits. A stratified sampling method was used to obtain the data. The association between study habits and academic performance was tested against each other through the chi-square test. The findings revealed that students' academic performance and study habits are significantly related.

Monica (2017) conducted a study on "Enhancement in Study Habit and Attitude of Higher Secondary School Students: A Study." The primary goal of the research was to examine the study habits, attitude and efficacy of the intervention module enhancement of study habits, attitude in school students. The purposive sampling technique was used in this study. The study reflected that the students experienced significant improvement in study habits. This shows that the intervention module is efficient in enhancing study skills.

Jhoselle et al. (2020) examined the relationship between academic performance and study habits of learners. The correlational approach was undertaken in this study. The results found that study habits and academic performance are not significantly correlated.

Aisma et al. (2020) conducted a study entitled "Study Habits of Students and Academic Achievement: A Correlational Study." The proposed study is an attempt to determine the relationship between the study habits scores (SHS) of students and their academic achievement. The findings indicated that the scores of the study habits of students and their academic performance have a positive relationship.

Objectives of the study:

- To explore the present status of study habits among the higher education students in the Hooghly district.
- To investigate the study habits level with respect to different demographic variables like Stream of study, Gender, Habitat, Family Structure, Caste, Dominating character of Family, and Siblings.
- To identify various challenges faced by UG Students in the Hooghly District

Hypotheses of the study:

- H₀₁. There is no significant difference between Male and Female undergraduate students in terms of their Study habit.
- H₀₂. There is no significant difference between Rural, Urban and Semi urban undergraduate students in terms of their Study habit.
- H₀₃. There is no significant difference between the undergraduate students of different Social Categories (SC, ST, OBC, UR and OTHERS) in terms of their Study habit.
- H₀₄. There is no significant difference between the undergraduate students of joint families and nuclear families in terms of their study habits.
- H₀₅. There is no significant difference between undergraduate students in Study habit across different numbers of their siblings.
- H₀₆. There is no significant difference between Arts, Commerce and Sci-

ence undergraduate students based on their study habits.

Methodology:

This study applied a quantitative approach. Researchers used the survey method to obtain data from higher education students of the Hooghly district, West Bengal, to find out the current state of learners' study habits and also used various secondary sources to know the challenges faced by UG students of the Hooghly district.

- **Population:** All undergraduate students studying in colleges of the Hooghly district in West Bengal were considered as the population of this study.
- **Sample & Sampling Technique:** A sample of 239 UG students from different colleges located in the Hooghly district was selected for the sample. Considering selected variables, this study used Simple random sampling techniques to select the sample.
- **Instrument was used:** It is very crucial for a study to gather relevant data to test the hypothesis. The researcher used the Study Habit Inventory, adapted from the University of Puget Sound Learning Centre, for the data collection. The Inventory was designed based on various dimensions such as concentration, time management, note-taking, learning strategies and exam preparation.
- **Scoring technique:** The study habit inventory includes 19 items, which are measured on a five-point Likert scale, that is Never (1), Rarely (2), Sometimes (3), Frequently (4), and Always (5). The score was decided through item-wise answer key and total scores of each respondent were obtained by summing responses of all items. On the basis of the inventory, total scores were categorised into different levels: Below 20 is considered ineffective study habits, 21-40 is Fair, 41-60 is Good and above 60 is Excellent study habits.

Delimitations of the study:

The study was delimited to only the Undergraduate Students, Hooghly district of West Bengal and Bengali medium college students.

Data analysis and Interpretation:

Data Analysis among Hooghly District colleges Undergraduate Students on the status of study habits, which means how their study habits are, what the level of their study habits, whether it's in poor level or an excellent level and any significant differences that exist based on multiple socio-demographic factors such as Gender, Habitat, Caste and Stream, etc. On the basis of the Normality test, different Parametric and Non-Parametric tests were used to test hypotheses.

Hypothesis-wise Data Analysis and Interpretations:

H₀₁. There is no significant difference between Female and Male undergraduate students in relation to their study habits scores.

Table 1. Mann-Whitney U test between male and female students

Test Statistics	
	Total Score of the Students
Mann-Whitney U	4550.500
Wilcoxon W	5775.500
Z	-.353
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.724
a. Grouping Variable: Gender of the Students	

Figure:1 Mean difference between the students of Male and Female

Interpretation:

From Table No. 1, it is noted that the calculated value (0.724) is greater than the level of significance (0.05). So, H_{01} is not rejected. Thus, it can be said that there is no significant difference between male and female students in terms of their study habits.

H_{02} . There is no significant difference between Rural, Urban and Semi urban in terms of their study habits scores.

Table 2. Kruskal-Wallis Test (H Test) between Rural, Urban & Semi Urban students:

Hypothesis Test Summary				
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of Total scores of independent categories of Habitat of the students.	Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.961	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

Figure:2. Habitat wise Mean distribution

Interpretation:

Table no. 2 says that the obtained p-value (.961) is more than the level of significance at the 0.05 level. So, it can be said that H_{02} is accepted. That means the habitat of students does not influence students' study habits in the Hooghly district.

H_{03} . There is no significant difference among the Social Category (SC, ST, OBC, UR and OTHERS) in terms of their Study habit scores.

Table 3. Chi-square Test between social categories of students:

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.144 ^a	9	.424
Likelihood Ratio	8.313	9	.503
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.212	1	.271
N of Valid Cases	241		

a. 7 cells (43.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

Figure 3. Social Category-wise Mean distribution

Interpretation:

From table no. 3, the calculated p-value (.424) is greater than 0.05 significance level. So, it is noted that the null hypothesis (H_0) is not rejected, there is no significant difference between social categories (SC, ST, OBC, UR and Others) with respect to their study habits.

H_{04} . There is no significant difference between students from joint and nuclear families in their study habits scores.

Table 4. Comparison of the status between the students of the joint family and the nuclear family

t-test: Independent Samples Test		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Total score of students	Equal variances assumed	.145	.704	2.320	239	.021	3.373	1.454
	Equal variances not assumed			2.321	148.949	.022	3.373	1.453

Figure 4. Family structure wise Mean distribution

Interpretation:

From table no 4, it is noticed that the calculated value (1.454) is less than the 0.05 significance level; therefore, H_{0_4} is rejected. The table above shows that students in joint and nuclear families differ significantly in their study habits.

H_{0_5} : There is no significant difference between the students in study habits across different numbers of their siblings.

Table 5. Chi-Square Tests between having siblings and no siblings:

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.298 ^a	3	.729
Likelihood Ratio	1.886	3	.596
Linear-by-Linear Association	.060	1	.806
N of Valid Cases	241		

a. 2 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .62.

Figure 5. Siblings-wise mean distribution:

Interpretation:

Table 5. says that the observed p-value (.729) is more than the 0.05 significance level. Hence, the H_{0_5} is not rejected. That means there is no significant difference between students in relation to their siblings with their study habits.

H_{0_6} . There is no significant difference between Arts, Commerce and Science students in terms of their study habits.

Table: 6 Kruskal-Wallis Test (H test) among Arts, Commerce & Science students:

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of TotalScore is the same across categories of StreamoftheStudy.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.796	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

Stream wise Mean distribution

Interpretation:

From Table 6, the obtained p-value (.796) is greater than the 0.05 significance level. So, the null hypothesis (H_0) is not rejected. There is no significant difference between Arts, Commerce and Science students based on their study habits.

Findings of the Study:

- No statistically significant difference was observed between Male and Female undergraduate students in relation to their Study habit. So the result indicated that male and female students of undergraduate colleges of the Hooghly district do not significantly differ based on their study habits.
- No significant difference existed between Rural, Urban and Semi-Urban students in terms of their study habits. The findings revealed that Rural, Urban and Semi-Urban undergraduate students are not significantly different based on their study habits.
- The study highlighted that there was no significant difference presented between the Social Category (SC, ST, OBC, UR and OTHERS) students in terms of their study habits. So, it can be noted that the null hypothesis was not rejected regarding the students' social category.
- A significant difference was observed between the students of joint family and nuclear family UG students in terms of their study habits. So, it can be identified that both groups, i.e. joint family and nuclear family students of Hooghly district, are significantly different based on their study habits.
- The study shows that there is no significant difference between the students in study habits across different numbers of their siblings. So, it can be stated that the null hypothesis was accepted in terms of the siblings of the students.
- No significant difference is evident among Arts, Commerce and Science students regarding their study habits. So, we can say that arts, commerce and science UG students are not significantly different with respect to their study habits.

Conclusion:

This study investigated undergraduate students' study habits in the Hooghly district on the basis of selected demographic variables such as gender, habitat, family structure, and stream etc. The study found that there is no difference in study habits among demographic variables such as habitat, gender, social category, stream of study and number of siblings. But there is a difference in the study habits of joint family and nuclear family students. Therefore, it can be suggested that family structure plays a significant role in shaping the study habits of students. Home Environment, Family interactions, and parents' supervision may affect students' study habits. Various challenges are also seen, such as limited resources,

family pressures, and socio-cultural constraints; many students show a willingness to improve their study habits.

Finally, it can be concluded that for good academic performance, it is necessary to regularly monitor the study habits of students, which will help them move forward in the field of education.

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